

LGHAP air pollutants dataset user guide (version 2)

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1. Descriptions of new version LGHAP dataset

LGHAP, the acronym of Long-term Gap-free High-resolution Air Pollutants concentration dataset, was generated via a big data analytics framework to provide gap free and high-resolution AOD, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, O₃, SO₂, CH₄, CO₂ and others concentrations to advance environment management and earth system science analysis. The LGHAP aerosol dataset in China has already been available and publicly accessible in 2021-11. The dataset was generated via a seamless integration of the tensor flow based multimodal data fusion with ensemble learning based knowledge transfer in statistical data mining. In our new version of LGHAP, leveraging an improved big earth data analytic framework with attention-reinforced tensor construction and adaptive background information updating schemes, gap-free AOD grids were firstly derived via an integration of multimodal AODs and air quality measurements acquired from diverse satellites, ground monitors, and numerical models. For better predicting PM_{2.5} concentration across the globe, a scene-aware ensemble learning graph attention network (SeGAT) was then developed to account for large modeling bias over regions with limited or even none in situ air quality measurements. For more details of the analytical framework of the big data analytics to generate the LGHAP v2 aerosol dataset, please refer to Bai et al. (2023) and Li et al. (2023).

In the current release of LGHAP aerosol dataset (LGHAP.v2), we provide a 22-year-long (2000–2021) gap free AOD and PM_{2.5} concentrations with daily 1-km resolution covering the global land area. Ground validation results indicate that the LGHAP.v2 AOD data are in a good agreement with *in situ* AOD observations from AERONET, with R of 0.85 and RMSE equaling to 0.14. Meanwhile, PM_{2.5} estimations also agreed well with ground measurements, with R of 0.95 and RMSE of 5.7 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Overall, the generated LGHAP aerosol dataset has a great potential to trigger multidisciplinary applications in earth observations, climate change, public health, ecosystem assessment, and environmental management.

Data users are encouraged to cite both the data set and the scientific publication given below when making use of these datasets:

Bai, K., Li, K., Tan, Z., Han, D., and Guo, J.: Daily 1-km gap-free AOD grids in China, v1 (2000–2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5652257>. Accessed DAY MONTH YEAR.

Bai, K., Li, K., Tan, Z., Han, D., and Guo, J.: Daily 1-km gap-free PM_{2.5} grids in China, v1 (2000–2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5652265>. Accessed DAY MONTH YEAR.

Bai, K., Li, K., Tan, Z., Han, D., and Guo, J.: Daily 1-km gap-free PM10 grids in China, v1 (2000–2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5652263>. Accessed DAY MONTH YEAR.

Bai, K., Li, K., Sun, Y., Wu, L., Zhang, Y., Chang, N., Li, Z., 2023. Global synthesis of two decades of research on improving PM2.5 estimation models from remote sensing and data science perspectives. *Earth-Science Rev.* 241, 104461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2023.104461>

Bai, K., Li, Ke, Ma, M., Li, Kaitao, Li, Z., Guo, J., Chang, N., Tan, Z., Han, D., 2022. LGHAP: the Long-term Gap-free High-resolution Air Pollutant concentration dataset, derived via tensor-flow-based multimodal data fusion. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 14, 907–927. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-14-907-2022>

Bai, K., Li, K., et al.: LGHAP: LGHAP v2: A global gap-free aerosol optical depth and PM2.5 concentration dataset derived via big earth data analytics since 2000, 2023. Under preparation

Li, K., Bai, K., et al.: A scene-aware ensemble learning graph attention network for global PM2.5 pollution mapping at 1km/daily resolution since 2000, 2023. Under preparation

2. Data format and naming conventions

The daily gap free AOD and PM_{2.5} concentrations map was provided separately in the NetCDF format, while data in each individual year were archived in a zip file.

The zip file was named after in a format such as *LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.Y2000.zip*. **LGHAP** is the dataset name. **AOD** is the product name, which can also be PM_{2.5} or other data product. **D001** indicates the resolution of data product as **D** means daily (temporal resolution) and **001** is the grid resolution of 0.01° (spatial resolution). **Y2000** is the time of the year (2000 in the case).

Similar naming convention is also applied to the daily product. For illustration, here we take the file of *LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A20200101.nc* as an example. The only difference is the time for the given file. For daily product, the time was given in a format of *Ayyyymmdd*. *yyyymmdd* is the date for the given data, in which *yyyy* is the calendar year, *mm* is the month and *dd* is the day-of-month number.

3. Example codes to read and visualize the LGHAP data

Below gives illustrative codes to help users read and visualize AOD data in LGHAP dataset using MATLAB, Python, R, and IDL programming language. Figure 1 shows the global map of

gap free AOD distribution in 2021 that was created with the LGHAP.v2 AOD dataset. Demo codes to read and visualize another product (PM_{2.5}) were also provided.

Figure. 1. The global map of gap free AOD distribution in 2021 that was created with the LGHAP.v2 AOD dataset.

MATLAB code:

```
% This demo provides an illustration on how to read and visualize AOD in  
% LGHAP dataset and write data into GeoTIFF in MATLAB.
```

```
%
```

```
% The demo was prepared with MATLAB R2020b.
```

```
%
```

```
% Last updated: 2023-11-28
```

```
%% (a) read AOD data from NetCDF file
```

```
% the nc file to be read
```

```
filename = 'LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A20141123.nc';
```

```
% read longitude and latitude from NetCDF file
```

```
lon = ncread(filename,'lon');
```

```
lat = ncread(filename,'lat');
```

```
% read AOD data
```

```
AOD = ncread(filename,'AOD');
```

```
%% (b) visualization
```

```
% create georeference struct to map AOD data on projected datum
```

```
R = georefcells([-58,62],[-180,180],[12000,36000]);
```

```
latlim = R.LatitudeLimits;
```

```

lonlim = R.LongitudeLimits;

% load coastlines
load coastlines

% plot data
pos = get(0,'ScreenSize');

figure('color','w','position',[50,50,round(pos(3)*0.5),round(pos(4)*0.5)]);

worldmap(latlim,lonlim)

% plot coastline
geoshow(coastlat,coastlon,'Color','k')

% plot AOD
geoshow(AOD,R,'DisplayType','surface');

% set colormap limits
caxis([0,2]);

% set colors used to map data
colormap('Jet');

% add colorbar
h = colorbar();
h.Label.String = 'AOD';
h.FontSize = 14;
setm(gca,'FontSize',14);

% add title to the plot
title(['Date',string(regexp(filename,'\d{8}','match'))], 'FontSize',14);

% save plot in jpg format with resolution of 300 DPI
savename = ['LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A' char(string(regexp(filename,'\d{8}','match')) ' .jpg'];
print(savename,'-djpeg','-r300');

%% (c) save as GeoTIFF

% define fillvalue
Fillvalue = -999;
AOD_tiff = AOD;
AOD_tiff(isnan(AOD_tiff)) = Fillvalue;

```

```
% write GeoTIFF
savename = ['LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A' char(string(regexp(filename, '\d{8}', 'match')))]'.tif'];
geotiffwrite(savename,AOD_tiff,R);
```

Python code:

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-  
''''
```

This demo provides an illustration on how to read and visualize AOD in LGHAP dataset and write data into GeoTIFF in Python.

netCDF4 is needed to read netCDF file

You can install this library by command: pip install netCDF4

The demo was prepared with Python3.7.

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```
''''
```

```
# import supporting library  
import netCDF4 as nc  
import numpy as np  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
from osgeo import gdal,osr  
import re  
  
## (a) read AOD data from NetCDF file  
# the nc file to be read  
filename = 'LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A20141123.nc'  
f = nc.Dataset(filename)  
  
# extract date from filename  
date = re.compile(r'\d{8}').findall(filename)  
  
# read longitude and latitude from NetCDF file  
lon = np.array(f['lon'][:])  
lat = np.array(f['lat'][:])  
  
# read AOD data  
AOD = np.array(f['AOD'][:])  
  
# replace missing value with nan  
AOD[AOD==65535] = np.nan  
  
## (b) visualization  
# create canvas  
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(17,10))
```

```

# plot AOD
im = ax.imshow(np.rot90(AOD,k=1),vmin = 0,vmax = 2,cmap = 'jet',extent =
[min(lon),max(lon),min(lat),max(lat)])

# set ticks and label
ax.set_xlabel('Longitude(°)',size=20)
ax.set_ylabel('Latitude(°)',size=20)
plt.xticks(fontsize=20)
plt.yticks(fontsize=20)

# add title
plt.title('Date:'+date[0],size=20)

# add colorbar
fig.subplots_adjust(right=0.9)
position = fig.add_axes([0.90,0.15,0.015,0.70])
cb = fig.colorbar(im,cax=position)
cb.ax.tick_params(labelsize=20)
cb.set_label('AOD',size=20)

# save plot in jpg format with resolution of 300 DPI
plt.savefig('LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A'+date[0]+'jpg',dpi=300)
plt.show()

## (c) save as GeoTIFF
# define fillvalue
AOD_tiff = AOD
AOD_tiff[np.isnan(AOD_tiff)] = -999

# write GeoTIFF
driver = gdal.GetDriverByName('GTiff')
dataset =
driver.Create('LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A'+date[0]+'tif',len(lon),len(lat),1,gdal.GDT_Float64)
dataset.SetGeoTransform([min(lon),0.01,0,max(lat),0,-0.01])
sr = osr.SpatialReference()
sr.SetWellKnownGeogCS('WGS84')
dataset.SetProjection(sr.ExportToWkt())
dataset.GetRasterBand(1).WriteArray(np.rot90(AOD_tiff,k=1))

# release memory
del dataset
f.close()

```

R code:

```
# This demo provides an illustration on how to read and visualize AOD in
# LGHAP dataset and write data into GeoTIFF in R.
#
# four libraries (ncdf4,raster,rgdal and ggplot2) are needed.
#
# The demo was prepared with R 3.6.1.
#
# Last updated: 2023-11-28
# install.packages

library(ncdf4) # package for netcdf manipulation
library(raster) # package for raster manipulation
library(rgdal) # package for geospatial analysis
library(ggplot2) # package for plotting

# set your path
setwd('.')

## (a) read AOD data from NetCDF file
# the nc file to be read
filename = "LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A20141123.nc"
ncdata = nc_open(filename)

# extract date from filename
date = substr(filename,regexpr("\\d{8}",filename),regexpr("\\d{8}",filename)+7)

# read longitude and latitude from NetCDF file
lon = ncvr_get(ncdata,'lon')
lat = ncvr_get(ncdata,'lat')

# read AOD data
AOD = ncvr_get(ncdata,'AOD')

# close nc file
nc_close(ncdata)

## (b) visualization
# convert AOD to raster in memory
r = raster(AOD, xmn=min(lon), xmx=max(lon), ymn=min(lat), ymx=max(lat),
crs=CRS("+proj=longlat +ellps=WGS84 +datum=WGS84 +no_defs+ towgs84=0,0,0"))
r = flip(r, direction='y')

# plot AOD and save plot in jpg format with resolution of 300 DPI
```

```
savename = paste(c('LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A',date,'.jpg'),collapse = "")
jpeg(file = savename,width = 5000,height = 4000,res = 300)
r2 = r
r2[r2>2]=2
plot(r2,col=topo.colors(100),main=paste(c("AOD Date: ",date),collapse = ""),zlim=c(0,2),xlab =
"Longitude", ylab = "Latitude",cex.axis=1.5,cex.lab=1.5,cex.main=2)
dev.off()
```

```
## (c) save as GeoTIFF
```

```
# write GeoTIFF
```

```
nc2raster = stack(r)
```

```
savename = paste(c('LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A',date,'.tif'),collapse = "")
```

```
writeRaster(nc2raster,savename,format = 'GTiff',overwrite = TRUE)
```

IDL code:

```
;This demo provides an illustration on how to read and visualize AOD in  
; LGHAP dataset and write data into GeoTIFF in IDL.
```

```
; The demo was prepared with IDL8.5.
```

```
; Last updated: 2023-11-28
```

```
PRO read_LGHAP_AOD
```

```
;Determine compilation rules
```

```
compile_opt idl2
```

```
;Set your path
```

```
envi, /restore_base_save_files
```

```
envi_batch_init
```

```
CD, '...'
```

```
outpath = '...'
```

```
; read AOD data from NetCDF file
```

```
filearr = dialog_pickfile(/multiple_files, title = 'Open the original nc file')
```

```
num = n_elements(filearr)
```

```
FOR i=0,num-1,1 DO BEGIN
```

```
file_ID = ncdf_open(filearr, /nowrite )
```

```
latid = NCDF_VARID(file_ID,'lat') ;read latitude from NetCDF file
```

```
NCDF_VARGET, file_ID, latid, lat
```

```
nlat = N_ELEMENTS(lat)
```

```
lonid = NCDF_VARID(file_ID,'lon') ;read longitude from NetCDF file
```

```
NCDF_VARGET, file_ID, lonid, lon
```

```
nlon = N_ELEMENTS(lon)
```

```
AODid = NCDF_VARID(file_ID,'AOD') ; read AOD data
```

```
NCDF_VARGET, file_ID, AODid, AOD
```

```
nAOD = N_ELEMENTS(AOD)
```

```
;Obtain the gain, offset, and fill values of AOD data, and perform calibration
```

```
ncdf_attget,file_ID,AODid,'scale_factor',a
```

```
ncdf_attget,file_ID,AODid,'add_offset',b
```

```
ncdf_attget,file_ID,AODid,'_FillValue',fv
```

```

fv_index = where(AOD eq fv)
output_AOD = (AOD ne fv)*AOD*a+b
; define fillvalue
output_AOD[fv_index] = -999

;visualization

loadct, 33
TVLCT, r, g, b, /get
color_table = BYTARR(3, 256)
color_table[0, *] = r
color_table[1, *] = g
color_table[2, *] = b
color_table[* , 0] = [255, 255, 255] ;Custom colorbar

img=image(transpose(output_AOD),rgb_table=color_table,title=file,grid_units=2,POSITION=[0.
1,0.15,0.9,0.95],map_projection='geographic', image_dimensions=[max(lon)-min(lon),max(lat)-
min(lat)] , $
    IMAGE_LOCATION=[min(lon),min(lat)],DIMENSIONS=[691,512])

;set colormap limits
img.MAX_VALUE=2
img.MIN_VALUE=0
;Change the figure title, grid type, axis text direction, and color bar form
img.title = 'Date:'+strmid(file_basename(filearr),16,8)

img.mapgrid.label_position=0
img.mapgrid.font_name='Palatino'

img.mapgrid.linestyle=6
img.mapgrid.horizon_thick=1

lons=img.mapgrid.longitudes
lats=img.mapgrid.latitudes
for lons_i=0,n_elements(lons)-1 do begin
    lons[lons_i].label_angle=0
    lons[lons_i].label_align=0
endfor

; add colorbar
c = COLORBAR(TARGET=img,
ORIENTATION=1,TITLE='AOD',POSITION=[0.905,0.25,0.925,0.85])
c.RANGE=[0,2]

```

```
c.BORDER=0
c.TICKDIR= 1
c.TEXTPOS = 1

;save plot in jpg format with resolution
save,outputpath+'LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A'+strmid(file_basename(filearr),16,8)+'.jpg'
; save as GeoTIFF
;Write geographic information structure
geo_info={
  MODELPIXELSCALETAG:[0.01,0.01,0.0],$
  MODELTIMEPOINTTAG:[0.0,0.0,0.0,min(lon),max(lat),0.0],$
  GTMODELTYPEGEOKEY:2,$
  GTRASTERTYPEGEOKEY:1,$
  GEOGRAPHICTYPEGEOKEY:4326,$
  GEOGCITATIONGEOKEY:'GCS_WGS_1984'}

;write GeoTIFF

WRITE_TIFF,outputpath+'LGHAP.Global_AOD.D001.A'+strmid(file_basename(filearr),16,8)+'.tif',re
verse(transpose(output_AOD),2),/float, geotiff=geo_info
;Close nc file ID
NCDF_CLOSE, file_ID
endfor

END
```